

A STUDY ON CONSUMERS EXPECTATION AND SATISFACTION TOWARDS MODERN DAY RETAIL SHOPS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO TIRUNELVELI

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Abstract

Retail sector plays a significant role in today business sector. Previous period few selected retail shop were provide a wide variety of products they enjoying domination market. At present the propensity of retail sector has been altered lot of modern retail shops were opened and also they grant a wide range of products and services. The traditional retail shops are now restructured. The foremost purpose of this paper analyse the consumers expectation and satisfaction level towards the modern retail shops in Tirunelveli city. This outcome may help and recognize the factors that control the consumers' expectations and satisfaction towards modern day retail shops. This paper also studies the consumer estimation and awareness about quality, price, products and services provided by modern day retail shop.

Keywords: Retailing, emerging trends, modern retail shops

Introduction

A modern retail store that sell lowest quantities of products or services to the consumer. A retail business that operate as a retail outlet. They naturally systematize buy goods from directly manufacturers or wholesaler at a size discount and fixing the price and selling the goods to end use of consumers. A retail shop or retailer is a business organization whole primary source is selling the goods to consumer. They concerned all the kinds of behavior of goods and service leaning straight to end use of consumer. The main aim of the retail shop is supply all kinds of products and service to their consumer at a rational price.

Emerging Trends in modern Retail Shops

Recent trends of Indian retailing sector lot of change, all the retail shops are completely restructured. Now a day's all the medias focus retail market like business press, newspaper, the chief executive officers, government officials of various sector are talk about it day to day current trend of Indian retail markets. At present the current Indian retail sectors give a choice of employment opportunities for both educated and uneducated people. The country's national income of retail sector also increased. The Government both central and state government gives more concession to the retail shops. Now a days the Indian retail sector is going away through anew conversion and emerging new markets. Both accessible and new player are concentrate new retail shops. In this paper make a challenge to evaluate the consumer expectation and satisfaction level towards modern day retail shop in Tirunelveli City.

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Emerging Trends in Modern Retail Shops in Tirunelveli

Tirunelveli is a major city of south Tamil Nadu., This city plays a major commercial and business role in state of Tamil Nadu. Tirunelveli District is one of the chief revenue-yielding districts in the state of Tamil Nadu. It is one of the top growing cities. Tirunelveli is otherwise called as twin city of Tirunelveli and Palayamkottai. Palayamkottai is called as oxford of South India. Modern retail shops in Tirunelveli so far is high street story with Reliance market, Big Bazaar, Aryas super market, Arasan super market, Ganesh departmental store etc.

People in Tirunelveli are able sufficient to knowledge to improve the standard life style of shopping, because mostly educated people play a major role in this city. The same time the people don't conscious the choices and options yet. Tirunelveli is mostly highs street centric and the locations are classified as traditional area, new high street, and emerging market areas. Traditional areas contain north and west car street in Tirunelveli town, where a new high street include Vannerpettai and Palayamkottai. Junction and Palayamkottai market play emerging market in Tirunelveli.

Statement of the Problem

Now a days the customers are more energetic customers. They look forward to branded items of quality, reasonable price, good service etc.... But the factors like high price, poor quality, poor service, poor response of customer care are highly dissolve their problems. At the same time the clients taste and preferences also change day by day, so the retailers are meet different problems in their retail shops for discovery the consumer expectation and perceptions. At this point concerning this present paper need to locate out the consumer belief and fulfillment towards modern retail shops in Tirunelveli city.

Scope of the Study

This paper gives a extensive study of the "Consumers Expectation and Satisfaction towards modern retail shops in Tirunelveli City". The scope of this to recognize the overall consumer perception and expectation, consumer satisfaction, product availability, quality of product, price awareness, products and services provided by the modern retail shops in Tirunelveli city. This study has been conducted and covering all the four zone of Tirunelveli city corporation.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the consumer expectation and satisfaction towards modern retail shops in Tirunelveli city.
2. To evaluate the level of satisfaction among the customers.
3. To identify the factors influence the customer's to purchase products in modern retail shops.
4. To make lawful the data and provide suggestions based on this study.

Research Methodology

1. **Research Design:** Descriptive research is adopted to analyze the consumer expectation and satisfaction towards modern retail shops.

Questionnaire method is used for this study. Primary data is composed through survey method.

2. **Area of the Study:** The questionnaire is conducted among all class of consumer who are ordinary and occasional buyer in the retail shops in Tirunelveli City.
3. **Sample Size:** The Sample size taken in this study is 120 respondents
4. **Data Usage:** The study is conducted both primary and secondary data
5. **Period of the Study:** The study was conducted for the period of December 2018 and January 2019
6. **Sample Technique:** Convenience Sampling method was adopted.
7. **Tools for analysis:** The collected data is analyzed with the help of statistical tools like simple percentage method, cross tabulation and Likert scale.
8. **Limitations of the Study:**
 - The area of this study is constrained to Tirunelveli City only
 - Only 120 respondents were preferred in this study. Hence the conclusions drawn are detailed and cannot be comprehensive.
 - Some of the few respondents not co-operate in this research study.
9. **Hypothesis:** There is no relationship between monthly income and average monthly purchase.

Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1: Demographic profile of the respondents

Sl. No.	Particulars	Classification	No. of Respondents	Percentage
01.	Gender	Male	76	63.34
		Female	44	36.66
02.	Age	Below 25 years	18	15
		Above 25 - 35	36	30
		Above 36 - 45	42	35
		More than 45 years	24	20
03.	Educational Qualification	School level	10	8.33
		ITI / Diploma	18	15
		Graduate	38	31.67
		Post Graduate	30	25
		Professional	24	20
04.	Monthly Income	Below ₹10,000	12	10
		₹10,001 - 15,000	26	21.67
		₹15,001 - 20,000	36	30
		₹20001 - 25,000	21	17.5
		Above 25,000	25	20.83
05.	Average monthly purchase	Below ₹1000	22	18.33
		₹1001 - 2000	26	21.67
		₹2001 - 3000	35	29.17
		₹3001 - 4,000	26	21.67
		Above ₹4000	11	9.17

Interpretation

From the above table, it is clearly shows that 63.34 % of the respondents are male and 36.66% of the respondents are female. Out of the

total respondents 15 % of the respondents are 25 years old and below. 30 % of the respondents age between 26 -35,35 % of the respondents belong to the age group 36 - 45, and20 % of the respondents are above 45 years age. Out of the total respondents 31.67 and 25 % of the respondents are graduates and post graduates respectively. 21.67 % of the respondents are in the income level of ₹ 10001 - 15,000. In this category 20.83 % of the respondents' income level is above ₹ 25,000. 35 % of the respondents spend ₹ 2001 - 3000 of their monthly budgets towards their purchase in the modern retail shops. Only 8.33 5 of the respondents spend more than ₹ 4000 for their purchase.

Table 2: Customer satisfaction regarding purchase

Sl. No.	Factors	Respondent's Response					Likert Scale		
		HDS	DS	No idea	S	HS	Weighted score	Total Score	Percentile points
1.	Service quality	03	08	18	39	52	489	600	81.5
2.	Product price	09	12	24	42	33	438	600	73
3.	Mode of payment	14	18	20	26	42	382	600	63.67
4.	Checkout process	10	16	22	34	38	434	600	72.33
5.	Easy accessibility	08	12	18	40	42	456	600	76
6.	Trolley facilities	07	13	21	51	28	440	600	73.33
7.	Home delivery	06	10	17	46	41	466	600	77.67
8.	Parking facility	10	16	20	33	41	439	600	73.17
9.	Time saving	07	13	17	29	54	470	600	78.33
10.	Visual merchandising	04	08	16	38	54	490	600	81.67

As per the above calculation a total 81.67 percentile shows better overall process of Visual merchandising. Service quality also fine with 81.5 percentile points. 72.33 percentile points regarding delay in checkout process

Table 3: Cross tabulation between monthly income and amount of average monthly purchase

Monthly Income	Amount of average monthly purchase					Total
	Below ₹1000	1001 - 2001	2001 - 3000	3001 - 4000	Above ₹4000	
Below ₹10000	5 (41.67)	4 (33.33)	1 (8.33)	1 (8.33)	1 (8.33)	12 (100)
₹10001 - 15000	7 (26.92)	8 (30.77)	5 (19.23)	4 (15.38)	2 (7.69)	26 (100)
₹15001 - 20000	6 (16.67)	9 (25)	14 (38.89)	5 (13.89)	2 (5.55)	36 (100)
₹20001 - 25000	2 (9.52)	2 (9.52)	6 (28.57)	8 (38.09)	3 (14.28)	21 (100)
Above ₹25000	2 (8)	3 (12)	9 (36)	8 (32)	3 (12)	25 (100)
Total	22 (18.33)	26 (21.67)	35 (29.17)	26 (21.67)	11 (7.86)	120 (100)

x²23.594-df16 ,sig. level26.296

The above table shows the frequency allocation of the respondents in terms of monthly income and amount of average monthly purchase of the retail shop in Tirunelveli city. The results show that out of 120 respondents 12 respondents' monthly income was below ₹ 10000 In this category 41.67 % of the respondents average monthly purchase was below ₹ 1000. 33.33 % of the respondents' average purchase was ₹ 1001 - 2000. 8.33 % of the respondents' average purchase was under this category ₹ 2001 - 3000, 3001 - 4000 and ₹ Above 4000. Out of the total respondents 26 respondents' monthly income was ₹ 10001 - 15,000. In this category of respondents 26.92 % of the respondents' average monthly purchase was below ₹1000. Only 2 respondents (7.69 %) average purchase above ₹ 4000. Out of the total respondents 36 respondents' monthly income was ₹ 15,001 - 20,000. In this category 14 (38.89) of the respondents' monthly purchase was ₹ 2001 - 3000. This table shows 21 respondents' monthly income was 20001 - 25,000. This category 8 (38.09 %) of the respondents' average purchase was ₹ 3001 - 4000. Out of the 120 respondents 25 respondents' monthly income was above ₹ 25,000. In this category 9 (36 %) respondents monthly purchase was ₹ 2001 - 3000 and 3 (12 %) respondents average monthly purchase was Above ₹ 4000.

From the above analysis, it is observed that the chi square test the calculated value of $\chi^2(23.584)$ is more than table value 26.296. The null hypothesis is rejected. It is concluded there is a relationship between the amount of monthly income and average monthly purchase in retail shop.

Conclusion

In this study noticeably explain that modern retail shops supply improved quality of product and service. Out of the total 120 respondents most of the respondents are satisfied with the quality of services obtainable by the modern retail shops in Tirunelveli city. They are satisfied with visual merchandising, service quality, and home delivery. Some of the customers respondents are not satisfied with checkout process, mode of payment and product price. This study noticeably shows by using chi square test there is no relationship between the amount of monthly income and average monthly purchase in retail shop. Modern are expect more service from modern retail shops. This study evidently shows most of the customers favor purchase from modern retail shops. Satisfaction of customer is one of the important aspects of the further development of modern retail shops. Retail shops are need to focus more extension activities.

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